

1. Zymogram patterns of peroxidase isozymes at 2-3 leaf stage (treated with butachlor). 1 = Yuan-Feng-Zao (S), 2 = Wu-Jie-Gu (R), 3 = Lu-Hong-Zao 1 (M), 4 = B3 (S), 5 = Long-Jiang-Dao (R), 6 = IR24 (S).

2. Zymogram patterns of esterase isozymes at 2-3 leaf stage (treated with butachlor). 1 = Yuan-Feng-Zao, 2 = Wu-Jie-Gu, 3 = Lu-Hong-Zao 1, 4 = B3, 5 = Long-Jiang-Dao, 6 = IR24.

existed only in susceptible varieties treated with butachlor; zymograms of samples from control and tolerant or medium varieties lacked the isozyme.

The fifth peroxidase isozyme and third esterase isozyme of B3 were slightly different in position from those of other varieties (Fig. 1, 2).

These results indicate that the tenth peroxidase and the third esterase isozyme of the three susceptible varieties are related to susceptibility. □

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Stress tolerance—drought

Influence of water potential on germination of direct seeded rice

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Germination of direct seeded rice is affected by soil moisture. We studied germination in local varieties Dharial and Katakara and improved varieties BR20 and BR21 in response to water potential.

Six levels of water potential (0, -176, -363, -514, -704, and -837 kPa) were created with 0, 0.5, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, and 0.25% NaCl solutions. Ten-ml aliquots of solution were added to 9.0-cm petri dishes containing Toyo 44 filter paper. Fifty seed/variety were placed on the

soaked filter paper and the covered dishes were kept on a laboratory bench at room temperature for 9 d. Germination percentages were recorded daily from day 4. Germination was virtually completed by day 8.

Germination of all four varieties was affected by water potential (see table). Maximum germination was at -176 kPa for all four varieties.

However, there was a significant variety x stress interaction. No significant differences in germination were observed from 0 to -514 kPa for Katakara and BR21. BR20 showed 75% germination at -704 kPa. At -837 kPa, Dharial failed to germinate.

Although using NaCl to impose water potential could also have caused salinity stress, it appears that BR20 has good tolerance for drought during germination. □

Germination of 4 rice varieties in response to water potential. BRRI, Bangladesh.

Water potential (kPa)	Germination ^a (%)				
	Dharial	Katakara	BR20	BR21	Mean
0	81 a	87 a	88 a	93 a	87
-176	83 a	90 a	91 a	93 a	89
-363	67 ab	84 a	91 a	89 a	83
-514	63 b	85 a	89 a	85 ab	81
-704	27 c	61 b	75 a	61 b	56
-837	03 d	37 c	27 b	14 c	20
Mean	54	74	77	73	

^aAv of 3 replications. Mean separation in a column by DMRT at the 5% level. LSD (0.05) for comparing variety means in row is 12%.

Stress tolerance-adverse temperature

Effect of synthetic phytohormone analog on leaf water potential during chilling

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We investigated the effect of a new synthetic analog of the phytohormone

abscisic acid (ABA), coded LAB173711 (BASF, FRG), on the water status of rice plants during chilling.

Low temperature-sensitive rice IR36 was sprayed at 36-d-old with 10⁻⁴ mol LAB173711/liter alone or a combination of LAB173711 with growth-retardant tetcyclacis. At 24 h after treatment, the seedlings were transferred to a water tank in the greenhouse and kept at a room temperature of 11 °C for 4 d. Leaf water potential

Effect of LAB173711 on leaf water potential of IR36 seedlings whose roots were kept at 11 °C in the greenhouse. IRRI, 1989.

was measured using a Scholander Pressure Bomb.

Leaf water potential (ψ_w) decreased significantly during chilling (-2.0 MPa in control). The decrease was minimized by the application of LAB173711 (-1.7 MPa) (see figure). The decrease was also lower in seedlings treated with LAB173711 and tetcyclacis (-1.6 MPa). Plants in the LAB173711 and LAB173711 + tetcyclacis treatments exhibited less yellowing than control plants.

The new synthetic ABA analog could be an effective tool in maintaining plant water status. □

A new phytohormone analog for preventing rice membrane injury after chilling

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We studied the effect on rice membrane stability of new abscisic acid (ABA) analog LAB173711 in combination with growth retardant tetcyclacis. Aqueous solutions of ABA, LAB173711, and LAB173711 + tetcyclacis (BASF, FRG), each at 10^{-4}

mol/liter, were sprayed on IR36 seedlings. After 24 h at 25 °C, the plants were transferred to 5 °C and kept for 3 d, then returned to 25 °C.

The second youngest leaf was cut off and immersed in 50 ml deionized distilled water, infiltrated under vacuum, and shaken for 1 h at room temperature. Electrolyte leakage was measured using a Cole-Parmer conductivity meter.

Membranes were injured in plants chilled for 3 d at 5 °C (see figure). Electrolyte leakage in plants sprayed with any of the three treatments was significantly lower. ABA decreased the leakage 9.18-fold; ABA analog LAB173711 alone, 6.35-fold.

LAB173711 + tetcyclacis was more effective; it decreased leakage 10.73-fold. □

Effect of LAB 173711 on electrolyte leakage from leaves of IR36 seedlings chilled at 5°C for 3 d. IRRI, 1989.

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Root cation exchange capacity (CEC) and yield-contributing parameters in rice in normal and alkali soils

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Alkali soils are reported to suffer from Ca deficiency and varieties with high root CEC are able to absorb relatively more cations. A relationship is reported to exist between root CEC and N uptake, and tolerance for soil alkalinity.

We studied the performance of eight rice varieties in normal soil (pH 7.8) and alkali soil (pH 9.5) in a pot experiment. NPK fertilizers were applied at 120, 26, and 49 ppm.

CEC of roots, air dry weight of roots, and length of roots were determined at active tillering 30 d after transplanting. Whole roots were thoroughly mixed and powdered to determine CEC. Plant height, fresh weight of shoot/plant, and grain test weight were recorded at harvest.

Table 1. Root characteristics in rice varieties grown in normal and alkali soils. Kanpur, India.

Variety	Root air-dry weight (g/pot)		Root length (cm)		Root CEC (meq/100 g)	
	Normal	Alkali	Normal	Alkali	Normal	Alkali
IR8	9.54	5.62	28	26	10.50	9.85
Jaya	8.31	4.07	30	27	9.75	8.25
M1-48	7.39	3.78	27	25	14.75	11.86
Pokkali	7.63	4.48	35	30	11.12	10.13
Pusa 2-21	5.2	4.47	32	28	12.75	7.90
Damodar	8.64	5.83	37	24	8.25	5.97
Saket 4	7.71	4.92	27	23	8.77	6.58
CSSR3	7.58	6.15	29	26	12.00	5.29
LSD (0.05)	0.42	0.38	3	2	1.82	1.35